

Review of health research and data on racialised minorities: Implications for addressing racism and racial disparities in public health practice and policies in Europe

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Abstract

To understand health disparities among racialised minorities, researchers must collect and use evidence-based data which will be used to inform decision-making and action on key structural and social determinants of health such as racism. This systematic search and review aims to contribute to this, and to improvements in equality and equity in health, by promoting a race-conscious approach to health research and strengthening the utilisation and deployment of data and research on racialised minorities in Europe. Concretely, this study will do so by reviewing and critically analysing the usage of the concepts of race, ethnicity and related euphemisms and proxies as well as the contemporary utilisation and deployment of data and research on racialised minorities in health research. The study will focus on Belgium, France and the Netherlands, three countries which have some geographical and cultural proximity. To conclude, the results will be used to develop guidance on how to utilise and deploy data and research on racialised minorities.

The review is part of a larger project which aims to promote race-conscious research and data. The project does this by taking a three-pronged approach which highlights the need for a race-conscious approach while using data and research on racialised minorities, builds expertise for their effective utilisation and deployment, and creates a knowledge network and community of practice for public health researchers working in Europe.

Introduction and rationale

While health disparities linked to the socially-constructed concepts of race¹ and ethnicity have long been established, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought renewed attention to the issue. Although most people have been affected by the pandemic, an increasing body of international research² shows that racialised minorities have been disproportionately affected in terms of disease exposure, susceptibility to the disease, severity of the disease and mortality rates. In addition to this, the measures taken to contain or mitigate the pandemic have had a particularly negative impact on the determinants of health and access to care for people within such groups. This has, in many cases, had negative consequences for their health statuses and health outcomes, which has ultimately, further increased existing health disparities among racialised minorities (Katikireddi et al., 2021). Addressing this will require evidence-based decision-making and action on key structural and social determinants of health like racism, which are mediated by race, ethnicity and related concepts.

Yet historically, in many countries across Europe, research on racialised minorities is not appropriately, adequately or sufficiently carried out. There are a few strands to this issue. One of these is a continuous emergence of biologically or genetically based race research which is often linked to scientific racism (Saini, 2019). Cerdeña, Plaisime and Tsai (2020), recognising this, introduced the race-conscious approach which, in contrast to the race-based approach, focuses on racism and racial health disparities. This race-conscious approach forms the basis and the goal of this project. Another strand is the issue of the poor utilisation and deployment of data and research on racialised minorities, for the monitoring and tackling of health disparities, and public health policymaking and social change, which this project focuses on (Farkas, 2017; Holtzman, A. Khoshkhoo & Nsoesie, 2022).

Data and research on racialised minorities is often underutilised and under-deployed for three broad reasons. The **first** reason is related to data use. In many countries, there is a lack of national data systems based on race, ethnicity and related concepts, which means that there is limited statistical evidence on health disparities among racialised groups. This situation is often exacerbated by the lack of recognition and undervaluing of data such as lived experiences, testimonies, and other similar forms of knowing. In addition to this, even in cases where data exists, and it is valued and recognised as such, it might still not be used for research, as many researchers lack the capacity and/or expertise to collect and analyse the data and interpret the results.

The **second** reason is linked to the research itself. There is a disinclination among certain researchers to carry out any research linked to race and/or ethnicity, as the use of such variables in research, continues to be seen as contentious, to some degree. While some researchers see these variables as valuable tools for analysing and addressing health inequalities as well as the impact of various forms of racism (institutionalised, systemic/structural, interpersonal, internalised racism) on racialised minority groups,

¹ The authors follow the widely accepted notion that race has no biological basis. Regardless, race exists as a social reality and thus has real consequences. See also: key definitions.

² See bibliography at the end of the document, and for Belgium specifically, see for example Vanthomme et al. (2021), for France, see Carillon et al. (2020); and for the Netherlands, see Coyer et al. (2021).

others oppose their use on the grounds that they can be misused and instrumentalised against racialised groups or used in ways that are sometimes difficult to anticipate for instance to fuel stigmatisation and racial stereotyping. Additionally, research on racialised minorities is often seen as too difficult to implement in practice, due to challenges of finding appropriate approaches and solutions to conceptualisation, operationalisation, data collection, interpretation, representativeness, transferability and generalisability. For instance, in cases where data is collected on racialised minority groups, it might be done in non-standardised ways which, according to some researchers, renders comparison pointless or in some cases even impossible.

The **third** reason focuses on the results of research on racialised minorities. In many cases where data on racialised minorities is available and it is being used for research, the results are frequently not used for advocacy, and/or the results and recommendations are not implemented or used to effect policy change and achieve real-life impact. This is amongst others, because the results are deemed to be too specific, subjective, or politicised. Many researchers also regard advocacy and activism as being beyond the scope of their mandate. Furthermore, similarly to broader society, within the field of health, there are strong tendencies to erase contributions from marginalised/racialised researchers or to erase race when analysing inequalities, as was for example the case with the concept of intersectionality in feminist studies³. In contrast, when the results are used in policymaking, this is generally done without sufficient attention to unintended consequences which means that in some cases, the results, instead of supporting efforts to tackle racial health disparities, actually (inadvertently) contribute to further entrenching them.

The consequence of all this for public health is the adoption and implementation of policies that are ostensibly race-neutral but which in fact reproduce “methodological whiteness”⁴ and create or exacerbate health inequities and inequalities amongst racialised minorities. This criticism is reflected in the widespread calls to decolonise health research, improve equality and equity in health in an intersectional way, and ultimately, achieve social and racial justice. These calls are being responded to at all levels of society. In 2018, for instance, the EU High Level Group on Non-discrimination, Equality and Diversity⁵ adopted a set of non-binding guidelines on how to improve the collection and use of equality data, compiled practices implemented at national level related to the set of guidelines and developed a diagnostic tool/checklist with which to assess the availability and quality of equality data collected at national level.

This project likewise aims to contribute to improving equality and equity in health, by promoting a race-conscious approach to health research and strengthening the utilisation and deployment of data and research on racialised minorities. We do so by taking a

³ See Bilge (2013)

⁴ See Bhambra 2017a, 2017b. “‘Methodological whiteness’, I suggest, is a way of reflecting on the world that fails to acknowledge the role played by race in the very structuring of that world, and of the ways in which knowledge is constructed and legitimated within it. It fails to recognise the dominance of ‘whiteness’ as anything other than the standard state of affairs and treats a limited perspective – that deriving from white experience – as a universal perspective. At the same time, it treats other perspectives as forms of identity politics explicable within its own universal (but parochial and lesser than its own supposedly universal) understandings.” (2017b)

⁵ See <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3328>

three-pronged approach which highlights the need for a race-conscious approach while using data and research on racialised minorities, builds expertise for their effective utilisation and deployment, and creates a knowledge network and community of practice for public health researchers working in Europe.

The project begins with a literature review which critically analyses the way race, ethnicity and related euphemisms and proxies are conceptualised, operationalised and used in public health research in three countries in continental Europe. It then goes on to critically examine, using literature from other countries on this issue, how research on racialised minorities is conducted. The results will then be used to develop guidance on how to utilise and deploy data and research on racialised minorities. Finally, as a follow-up to the review, our findings will be stored in a knowledge repository that is accessible to health researchers. The overarching goal is to contribute to addressing health disparities among racialised minorities, across Europe.

Key definitions

1. Race: Refers to socially constructed differences among people based on characteristics such as skin colour, physical characteristics, accent or manner of speech, name, clothing, diet, beliefs and practices, leisure preferences, places of origin and so forth. There is no scientifically supported biological basis for racial categorisation, however, societies construct races as 'real', and this has different and unequal implications for economic, political, social and cultural life⁶.
2. Ethnicity: A multi-dimensional social construct based on cultural distinctiveness and shared group cultural identity and characteristics. Examples of ethnic characteristics are, amongst others, language, and cultural norms, which are sometimes linked to religion and nationality. Different from, but closely related to race⁷.
3. Racial and ethnic euphemisms and proxies: A word or an expression which is used to denote and describe racialised minorities, in cases when "race" and "ethnicity"⁸ are considered inappropriate or inadequate, or in order to depoliticise and deracialise these concepts. This includes the use of terms which are related to concepts like migration, religion, language, postcode, citizenship, and culture.
4. Racialisation: A complex, contradictory and arbitrary process through which groups and individuals come to be designated as being of a particular 'race' and on that basis subjected to differential and/or unequal treatment. Put simply, racialisation is "the process of manufacturing and utilising the notion of race in any capacity"⁹. While white people are also racialised, this process is often rendered invisible or normative to those designated as white. As a result, white people may not see themselves as part of a race but still maintain the authority to

⁶ Inspired by CIHI (2022)

⁷ Inspired by CIHI (2022)

⁸ It has to be noted here that the concept of ethnicity is itself sometimes used as a proxy to not talk about race. See Song (2017)

⁹ Dalal (2002, p. 27)

name and racialise “others.” The individual and group identities of members of racialised groups shape both their relationships and interactions between each other, as well as with members of the out-group, and it influences social practice, and engagements with time, space, social structures and institutional systems. Racialisation thus has impacts on every aspect of life¹⁰.

5. Racialised minorities: Refers to groups that are subject to racialisation and are also minoritised based on various characteristics such as migration status, citizenship, religion, culture, language or geographic location. To emphasise the process of racialisation, some authors use the term ‘racially minoritised people’.
6. Racism: “Organised systems within societies that cause avoidable and unfair inequalities in power, resources, capacities and opportunities¹¹” among racialised minorities. “Racism can manifest through beliefs, stereotypes, prejudices or discrimination. This encompasses everything from open threats and insults to phenomena deeply embedded in social systems and structures. Racism can occur at multiple levels, including: internalised (the incorporation of racist attitudes, beliefs or ideologies into one’s worldview), interpersonal (interactions between individuals) and systemic (for example, the racist control of and access to labour, material and symbolic resources within a society)¹²”.
7. Inequality: Refers to the unequal and/or unjust distribution of resources and opportunities among members of a given society.
8. Inequity: Refers to the avoidable or remediable systemic disparities which occur in groups that are defined socially, economically, demographically or geographically within a given society, regardless of whether there is equitable and/or just distribution of resources and opportunities among members of the society.
9. Health disparities: Refers to a condition “in which disadvantaged social groups such as the poor, racial/ethnic minorities, women and other groups who have persistently experienced social disadvantage or discrimination systematically experience worse health or greater health risks than more advantaged social groups”(Braveman, 2004; 2007). When systemic barriers to good health are avoidable yet still remain, they are often referred to as ‘health inequities’.¹³
10. Racial health disparities: Refers to health disparities that occur amongst racialised minority groups. It describes the increased presence and severity of certain diseases, poorer health outcomes, and greater difficulty in obtaining healthcare services.

¹⁰ Inspired by SOURCE: Alberta Civil Liberties Research Centre, “Racialization” (2018) / Calgary Anti-Racism Education, “CARED Glossary” (2020)

¹¹ Informed by Paradies (2015)

¹² Informed by Paradies (2015)

¹³ What Is Health Inequity?, see <https://www.vdh.virginia.gov/health-equity/unnatural-causes-is-inequality-making-us-sick/what-is-health-inequity/#:~:text=%E2%80%9CDifferences%20in%20health%20status%20among,living%20in%20various%20geographic%20localities.%E2%80%9D> (site visited June 22, 2022)

11. Intersectionality: “The complex, cumulative way in which the effects of multiple forms of discrimination (such as racism, sexism, and classism) combine, overlap, or intersect especially in the experiences of marginalized individuals or groups” (Crenshaw, 1989).
12. Race-based approach: Based on a biologically essentialist conception of race according to which all members of a racial category are believed to have defined shared physical or genetic characteristics, or a specific biological essence. This assumption allows the members of the group to be seen, both by themselves and by others, not as individuals with personal traits, but rather as prototypes of the collective with identical traits and characteristics, which leads to stereotyping, essentialisation, fixity, homogenisation.
13. Race-conscious approach: Focuses on racial discrimination and racism as central issues, in contrast to the race-based approach. As a reference point, Cerdeña, Plaisime and Tsai (2020) introduce “race-conscious medicine as an alternative approach that emphasises racism, rather than race, as a key determinant of illness and health, encouraging providers to focus only on the most relevant data to mitigate health inequities”.
14. Racial justice in health: Using the race-conscious approach to tackle racial health disparities and injustices and improve health among racialised minorities in an intersectional way, with the aim of advancing equality and equity in health and ultimately, achieving social and racial justice¹⁴.
15. Data: Any type of information that is collected to be examined, considered and used for research as well as to support decision-making. This includes quantitative information, such as measurements and calculations, and qualitative information, such as lived experiences and blog posts¹⁵.
16. Research: “A detailed study of a subject, especially in order to discover (new) information or reach a (new) understanding¹⁶”, which involves “weaving together different strands of information, thought, and data¹⁷”, amongst others, in order to contextualise both the research and its findings.

¹⁴ Inspired by Reference to the Praxis Project: see health law as social justice, 2014

¹⁵ Inspired by <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/data>

¹⁶ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/research>

¹⁷ <https://blog.scienceopen.com/2016/05/why-context-is-important-for-research/>

Objectives

The objectives of the literature review are to:

1. Examine which data is used to address racial health disparities in health research
2. Examine how data on racialised minorities is collected, analysed, interpreted in health research
3. Critically analyse the way race, ethnicity and related euphemisms and proxies are conceptualised, operationalised and used in health research
4. Develop guidance on how to appropriately utilise and deploy data on racialised minorities, how to undertake race--conscious research and how to effectively use the results to address racial health disparities

Scope of the research

Thematic scope: The review will take race and ethnicity in health research as a focus of analysis. It will expand to include related euphemisms and proxies such as migration, citizenship, religion, culture, language, postcodes, as well as other characteristics which influence and shape health inequities, such as gender, sexuality, disability, age, socio-economic condition, and geographic location. This will ensure that we integrate relevant intersecting determinants of health inequalities and inequities in our analysis of health disparities among racialised minorities. It will also allow us to draw attention to the complex and often neglected interplay of various forms of vulnerabilisation.

Geographical context: The review will focus on research on Belgium, France and the Netherlands, three countries in continental Europe which have been selected for their geographical, linguistic and cultural similarities.

Timespan: The review will cover the period between 2018 until 2022 which will allow us to take into account data and research on racialised minorities from just before, during and after the most acute phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. This is because, as argued above, the COVID-19 pandemic has led to an increased focus and attention on the issue of health disparities among racialised minorities.

Methods

A systematic search and review approach will be taken to this review, as this combines strengths of a critical review with those of an exhaustive search process. This approach is especially appropriate for the review because by facilitating the comprehensive exploration of what is known about the topic, it will support the synthesis of best evidence and consequently, the generation of recommendations for practice (Grant and Booth, 2009).

Review questions

The questions which will guide the review as follows:

1. What concepts are used for health research on racialised minorities, and how are they operationalised?
2. What type of data on race, ethnicity and related euphemisms and proxies are used, and why?
3. How is research on racialised minorities carried out?
4. What are best practices on research and the use of data on racialised minorities, and why?

Data collection

Databases

The databases listed below will be used in this review. They were chosen for their large collections of both peer-reviewed and grey literature, which will ensure that we can capture the variety of published information on the subject matter.

- Google scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/>
- PubMed <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
- Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/home.uri>
- Bielefeld Academic Search Engine: <https://base-search.net/>
- Proquest: <https://www.proquest.com/>
- Persée (French) : <https://www.persee.fr/>
- Narcis (Dutch): <https://www.narcis.nl/>
- FRIS (Belgian): <https://researchportal.be/>

Search strategy

The search strategy was developed by creating a list of search terms that are relevant to the research questions and combining them as follows: 'race' OR 'racial' OR 'ethnicity' OR 'ethnic' OR 'migrant' OR 'migration' OR 'immigrant' OR 'foreign' OR 'non-citizen' OR 'nationality' OR 'third country national' OR 'refugee' OR 'asylum' OR 'allochthonous' OR 'ancestry' OR 'undocumented' OR 'illegal' OR 'irregular' OR 'resident' OR 'residence' OR 'religion' OR 'religious' OR 'minority' OR 'minorities' OR 'roma' OR 'gypsy' OR 'Traveller' OR 'cultural, OR 'culture', OR 'language' OR 'linguistic', OR 'postcode' OR 'neighborhood' OR 'neighbourhood' OR 'marginalized' OR 'marginalised' OR 'community' OR 'communities' OR 'population group' OR 'vulnerable' OR 'precarious' OR 'family background' OR 'heritage' OR 'origin' **AND**

'health inequalities' OR 'health inequities' OR 'health disparities' OR 'determinants of health' **AND** 'health research' OR 'health' **AND** 'Belgium' OR 'France' OR 'The Netherlands'.

Given that this protocol was written in the very early stages of the review process, we see the above as a non-exhaustive list. We will translate in French and Dutch the search terms and will use the translated terms in these 3 databases: Persée, Narcis, FRIS. We will therefore take an inductive approach, in which we allow concepts that emerge from the review to further inform the search strategy. A table of the exact search strings used for each database as well as the specific search fields used, will be provided in the Annex 2 at the end of the review.

The results of the search strategy will be refined by language and date to include only publications that were written in English, French and Dutch and which were published from 2018 onwards.

The database searches will be supplemented by reference mining of the selected publications to ensure that relevant documents or articles that might have been missed, are identified and included. In addition, manual searching of websites of key actors and organisations will be carried out to identify relevant grey literature we might have missed in the database searches.

Selection process

The citations produced by the search strategy will be screened for relevance and for inclusion in the study. To be eligible, the article or report must have both health **and** race, ethnicity or related concepts as its subject matter.

The types of documents to be included will be peer-reviewed primary studies and reviews; preprints; commentaries; editorials, published in a scientific journal and of which a full-text version is available. In addition to this, we also include published grey literature where the full text is available online.

Data extraction

Approximately 30 variables will be extracted from the publications that are included in the review. This will include information on the:

1. Publication (title, year of publication, author(s) and their affiliation, journal, type of document)
2. Concepts that are used for health research on racialised minorities and how they are operationalised
3. Data and data collection
4. Research methodology and methods

Data management

Citations generated from the search strategy will be reviewed using the Covidence software which will be used to identify publications for inclusion in the review. These will then be uploaded and stored in a Zotero library. The data extracted from the

included publications will be organised using Microsoft Office 2021 Excel, and stored on a secure server.

Data analysis

First, a descriptive analysis will be done to provide an overview of the data that is extracted from the included publications, using quantitative and qualitative methods.

Following this, a critical analysis will be undertaken to identify the:

1. Concepts that are used for health research on racialised minorities, and how are they operationalised
2. Types of data on race, ethnicity and related euphemisms and proxies that are used, and arguments put forward to justify their use
3. Methodology and methods that are used for research on racialised minorities, with a particular focus on innovative approaches and methods

The results of the critical analysis will then be used to inform the development of guidelines for best practices in the use and deployment of data and research in racialised minorities, with the aim of addressing health disparities.

Reporting and registration

The review protocol will be registered and peer-reviewed on the Open Research Platform F1000Research <https://f1000research.com/>

Review team

Core group (Clara Affun-Adegbulu, Theo Cosaert, Marie Meudec) and extended project group

Data availability

The list of references used in the review will be stored on Zotero, while the project documents will be stored on the Data Science Hub / ITM website. Both the review references and project documents will be open access and freely accessible to the public.

Dissemination

The finalised review protocol will be shared online on F1000research website. The review results will be shared and discussed during conferences (AfroEuropeans Conference: September 2022; European Public Health Conference: November 2022) and seminars at the Institute of Tropical Medicine (Belgium). The review results will also be submitted to a scientific journal after finalisation.

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